

GENDER EQUALITY IN THE WORLD AND ITS ANALYSIS AT THE LEVEL OF AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The gender problem, which has existed throughout history, has always been a cause of dissatisfaction and has become one of the pressing problems in many countries. Gender inequality manifests itself in social, economic, and other areas, hinders the progress of these areas, lowers its efficiency, and leads to social injustice in society. In our study, the factors that condition and cause gender inequality were discussed, and numerous steps and measures taken to prevent this process, not only in the backward countries of the world but also in developed countries, were discussed. We will analyze gender equality based on the results of a survey conducted in the society of Azerbaijan, an Eastern country.

Keywords: gender equality, Gender inequality in Eastern and Western countries, "All discrimination against women on cancellation of forms" to the Convention, gender equality in Azerbaijan, "UN-Women."

INTRODUCTION

The problems caused by a person's birth were his companions and were formed together with him. Interestingly, as society develops, these problems become more complicated instead of being solved. "Gender inequality," which we will write about, has always been a controversial issue throughout human history. Even today, this problem remains relevant and manifests in different forms in different regions of the world. To deeply understand this concept, which will be analyzed in our article, we need to clarify what the concept of "gender" is. At the end of the last century, the idea of "Gender" was formed, which sociologists characterized as "Social sex." Women's movements form the basis of the concept of "gender," which was brought to the lexicon of the world's peoples for nearly two centuries. Many definitions of this term are known. But in general, "gender" refers to the social role of women and men in society - social equality between women and men is considered gender equality.

The concept of gender equality and the factors that create conditions for the violation of equality

It is an indisputable fact that for the formation of a healthy family environment, women and men in society must be equal from a legal, social, and spiritual point of view. This equality entered our lexicon in the form of "gender equality." Gender equality means the equality of men and women in all spheres of social life. Various laws have been adopted in many developed countries to regulate this equality, and certain steps have been taken. But the problem of ensuring gender equality remains relevant. (1)

Let's give a general definition of this concept. Gender equality, which is related to human rights, is the granting of equal opportunities and rights of participation to men and women in all areas of society, as well as in private life. Like all human rights, gender equality must be fought for, defended, and promoted. Every day, girls and boys become living witnesses to

gender inequality in their homes and communities—in the media and among the adults who care for them.

Unfortunately, women and sexual minorities are subjected to injustice and violence in various parts of the world today. Gender equality is a condition that must be ensured for a peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world. Now let's analyze this concept and the reasons behind it in depth. (2)

Gender inequality: What are the causes?

Gender inequality is a social and cultural phenomenon in which people are discriminated against based on their sex. Basically, it is between a woman and a man. We can feel the effect of this phenomenon in different areas: at work, in social life, in family life, etc. This process, encountered by many of us, has become commonplace.

For example, socially, women are forced to obey their husbands or fathers; economically, women are still paid less than men for the same job positions (wage gap). When it comes to housework and child care, most people still think that these responsibilities belong more to women than to men. This list can be continued.

When faced with such a list, feminism or gender perspectives allow us to look at the world from another perspective. However, changing your perspective may make you feel some discomfort or confusion. So the purpose of this article is to clear your mind. So you can connect and place yourself more evenly in the world.

Let's start from the beginning. What do we mean by the word "gender" when we talk about gender inequality? What do we mean by such a large structure? (3)

What is gender, and how is it constructed?

Gender can be divided into three aspects:

Sociocultural field: In this respect, gender is a system of social organization that gives men more power and privileges. It is supported by beliefs that legitimize and perpetuate this social structure.

Attitude domain: Gender is a dynamic process. It reflects what it means to be a man or a woman in our

daily lives. In turn, it affects the behavior of men and women.

Personal Space: This gender is a collection of interests, fantasies, and beliefs that affect personality and personal relationships. They associate what it means to be male or female with more or less acceptable models.

It should be noted that gender is expressed in different ways depending on the culture. Furthermore, the degree of subjugation of women varies over time and geographical regions. Unfortunately, it isn't easy to find a culture where women have more political and social advantages than men. We can see that inequality or an unequal gender situation leads to high violence against women. These include sexual exploitation, kidnapping, rape, ill-treatment, sexual violence, and sexual harassment.

Below are some examples of gender equality and how it can be applied in everyday life and society. (3)

Example 1: Gender equality at home

Given that the foundation of society is the family, we can see its significant influence in this regard as well. Thus, the home is the place where people spend most of their time and is often the first place where children learn gender discrimination. Girls are usually taught that women are responsible for cooking, cleaning, and dressing. They are responsible for washing and other household chores; in contrast, men are not responsible for many household chores. This mindset has worked against women for millennia. The solution is for parents to first practice gender equality in the home, that is, to teach their children of all genders household responsibilities to delegate household chores equally and prepare them to take care of their future homes as adults. (3)

Example 2: Gender equality in the workplace ("Glass ceiling")

In the literature, the inability of women to reach high positions in business life is explained by the concept of "invisible" obstacles and "glass ceilings." We call them invisible barriers because they are never openly voiced. For unknown reasons, female candidates who want a high position face a glass ceiling when they hope to be promoted. While the laws give equal rights to women and men, gender discrimination is prohibited, and measures are taken against discrimination in workplaces; this time, glass ceilings prevent women from advancing in positions. Let's note that the "glass ceiling" term was used in the 1970s to describe the prejudices that prevented women from reaching top management positions in the United States and was coined in a 1986 Wall Street Journal story. This concept expresses the obstacles women face when they want to reach high positions in companies, government offices, educational institutions, or non-profit organizations.

Looking at the statistics, we see that women make up 49.5% of the world's population. This is equal to half of the human potential in a global sense. It has already been proven that economic development in countries has increased as a result of the active involvement of women in society and social life. Experts have studied women's and men's rights in 187 countries over the past

ten years and compared them on 35 criteria - from family, property, and labor rights to freedom of movement and personal safety. Of course, when the calculations were made, researchers also considered changes in legislation and reforms related to gender equality issues. According to the information we received, significant work is being done to eliminate gender inequality in European and Central Asian countries.

As we know, the "Covid-19" virus, which recently took the whole world into its sphere of influence, forced people to live in quarantine conditions in one way or another. According to experts, the coronavirus has completely changed the world. These changes have positive and negative sides. For example, the consequences of the pandemic had a negative impact on gender. Thus, the World Economic Forum (WEF) declared that the coronavirus pandemic increased gender inequality. According to the international organization's calculations, unfortunately, it will take 36 years longer than previously thought to eliminate this deficiency. According to the estimates of the World Economic Forum, the rate of elimination of gender inequality has decreased by 0.6% compared to last year due to the slowdown in large countries. This means that it will now take approximately 135.6 years to close the global gender gap. The WEF notes that the most affected areas after the COVID-19 pandemic are the workplaces where women turn to find work. Thus, women quarantine during the period; they seem to work "in two shifts": working from home, i.e., "home office," and doing housework in order to fulfill the social status they carry properly.

In addition, the report states that gender equality in the world is also being violated in the political arena. For example, it is shown that until January 15, 2021, 81 countries had never had a female head of state. According to the WEF study, which conducted research in 156 countries, only 26.1% of the approximately 35,500 parliamentarians worldwide; Out of more than 3.4 thousand ministers, only 22.6% are women.

There is almost no gender inequality in education and healthcare. In general, according to statistics, the gender balance in the field of education in the world is 95%. It should be noted that 37 countries have already achieved full gender equality. (3)

Gender Equality in Eastern and Western Countries

Under this article's title, we will analyze the factor of gender inequality in different parts of the world.

Just as the countries of the world are at different stages of economic development, they also have different contexts and problems related to gender equality. However, some general trends reflect the status of men and women and their expected roles in the labor market based on values and traditions in society and within the family.

For example, Soviet legislation contained provisions that ensured equal opportunities for men and women, including in the economic and labor spheres. However, during the Soviet era, women tended to engage in more "female" professions, spent more time raising children, and were provided with various

rewards and benefits by the state. Women could easily return to their previous jobs with the state guarantee against unemployment. At the same time, men traditionally functioned as breadwinners and held higher positions, including decision-making, although a quota of 30% of these positions was provided for women. During the transition, many women had to leave the formal economy for the informal sector to support their families, which resulted in a loss of social protection and job security. Today, women's economic activity in the region remains quite high, with about 80 women for every 100 men. At the same time, the share of women in fast-growing and high-paying sectors is declining, industrial and occupational segregation is increasing, and more women are long-term unemployed.

"Gender Equality" in Italy

Is there inequality in Italy?

The results shed more light on the multifaceted nature of inequality in Italy: the youngest individuals, women, and southern regions are particularly exposed to rising inequality.

The development of gender equality in Italy.

Italy scores 63.8 out of 100 in EIGE's Gender Equality Index 2021. Italy ranks 14th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index. Its score is 3.6 points lower than the EU score. (4)

What are gender roles in Italy?

Although men and women have equal rights under the law in this country, society is still primarily dominated by men. Within the family dynamic, the man is usually the patriarch and is considered the primary breadwinner. Traditionally, a woman was expected to fulfill the roles of marriage and motherhood. (5)

We can say that Italy has made progress in recent years in terms of legal protection. The country has introduced laws to combat gender-based violence and harassment and measures to create equal pay and opportunities for women in the workplace. However, significant cultural and social barriers still exist that prevent women from achieving true equality. In Italy, women continue to face discrimination and prejudice in many areas of life, including education, employment, and politics. In order to solve these problems, there is a need for continuous advocacy and awareness around gender equality issues. This includes encouraging women's leadership and participation in decision-making processes and challenging harmful gender stereotypes and norms. (6)

"Gender Equality" in Turkey

Looking at the Turkish Penal Code of 2005 (Articles 5 and 122), we see that to ensure gender equality; it is clearly stated that "no discrimination should be made between persons based on their sex". At the same time, the Turkish Civil Code of 2001 states adopted legal measures to ensure gender equality. (7)

Gender equality in Turkey has been a topic of discussion and debate for many years. Although there has been some progress in recent years, significant challenges remain to be addressed.

One of the main issues is violence against women. Turkey is one of the most femicide countries in the world, with hundreds of women killed each year, and

of course, we often see news like this on social media. The government has taken some steps to address this problem; for example, in 2012, due to domestic violence passed, a law increased the penalties. However, many activists argue that more needs to be done to protect women and bring perpetrators to justice.

Another issue is women's participation in labor. Although women make up about half of the population in Turkey, they are significantly underrepresented in the workforce. This is partly due to cultural attitudes that place women in charge of housework and child-rearing. The government has implemented policies to encourage women's labor force participation, such as providing tax incentives to companies that hire women. However, progress could be faster. (8)

There are also concerns about women's access to education and health services. Although Turkey has made significant progress in these areas in recent years, inequalities between men and women still exist. For example, women living in rural areas have less access to health services than men, and girls are more likely to drop out of school than boys. (9)

Overall, while there has been some progress in gender equality in Turkey, there is still a long way to go. This will require a concerted effort by government, civil society, and individuals to address the root causes of gender inequality and create a more equal society for all. (10)

"Gender Equality" in India

Discrimination against women and girls is a widespread and long-standing phenomenon that characterizes Indian society at all levels. Gender inequality in India results in unequal opportunities, and although it affects the lives of both sexes, statistically, we see that girls are the most disadvantaged.

Globally, girls have higher survival rates at birth, are more likely to be on the developmental track, and are more likely to attend preschool, but India is the only major country where more girls die than boys. And yet girls are also more likely to drop out of school.

India's progress towards gender equality, as measured by its position in rankings such as the Gender Development Index, has been disappointing despite fairly rapid economic growth rates.

Policy changes aimed at equalizing land inheritance rights between sons and daughters have met with a more mixed response. On the one hand, this has led to an increase in girls' education levels and marriage age, but on the other hand, it has increased marital conflict and led to domestic violence. For India to maintain its position as a global growth leader, more concerted efforts at the local and national levels and in the private sector are needed to bring women on par with men.

While increasing women's representation in public spheres is important and can potentially be achieved through some form of affirmative action, attitudinal change is essential for women to be recognized as equals in their own homes and in the wider society.

We can say that educating Indian children about the importance of gender equality from an early age can be a meaningful start in this direction. (11)

"Gender Equality" in Iran

As we know, Iran is one of the countries where women's rights are restricted the most. Here, women are described as second-class citizens and are deprived of many human rights. Unfortunately, this violation of women's rights continues in the 21st century.

Javid Rahman, the special rapporteur on the situation of human rights in the Islamic Republic of Iran, said: Child marriage is one of the most disturbing issues when talking about the rights of women and girls in Iran today. (12)

"The government and other leaders in the country should immediately raise the age of marriage and implement more policies and programs to reduce this practice in the country."

According to the law, a 13-year-old girl can get married, and younger girls can get married legally with the consent of the court and the father. According to the official information of the government, more than 16 thousand girls aged 10-14 got married in the first half of the current Iranian calendar year. "Currently, the legal age of marriage is absolutely unacceptable. It is clear that child marriage is harmful to girls' development and well-being, including their education, employment, and lives free from violence. (13)

The rights and legal status of Iranian women have changed since the beginning of the 20th century, especially during the last three regimes. During the Qajar dynasty, which ruled Iran from the late 1800s to the early 20th century, women were marginalized; they were not involved in politics, and their economic contribution was limited to household work. These conditions changed during the Pahlavi dynasty, which ruled the country from 1925 to 1979; women gained more freedom. Women's rights and freedoms were established as part of the leader's desire to transform Iran into a more modern, European-style country, although this was largely applied to the country's elites rather than the majority of the population. These freedoms were taken back after the 1979 Iranian Revolution. "Women's rights are severely restricted in Iran," Human Rights Watch said in 2015. Under Ebrahim Raisi, Iranian authorities increased control over women's dress codes, leading to a decline in women's rights. Iran's civil legal system is riddled with numerous laws that favor men over women, and with very few laws, it can be considered very different in terms of gender. Iran follows Islamic law. Under Iranian civil law, when children reach the age of majority, they also acquire criminal responsibility and can be tried as if they were legally adults. This can be seen as a disadvantage for girls who reach puberty at ten and boys at fourteen. This means that girls as young as ten can be prosecuted. Punishments can range from imprisonment to flogging and death, and women are prohibited from traveling without their husband's consent. Under Article 18 of the Passport Law passed in 1973, a husband can prohibit his wife from leaving the country. According to Iranian law, a woman must obtain her husband's permission before leaving the country or obtaining a passport. (14)

The situation has become tense in the modern era, and the beginning of this began with the killing of 22-year-old Mahsa Amin by the police in September.

Amini's death sparked sustained protests led by women and youth after she was arrested for allegedly violating the country's conservative dress code for women. Despite numerous protests, as we have seen, it remains fruitless. As we can see, Iran is one of the countries where gender equality is most violated, where exactly women's rights and freedoms are restricted. (15)

"Gender Equality" in France

Gender inequality persists around the world. Faced with this, France is increasing the consistency and effectiveness of gender measures in development aid policy and foreign action. The 3rd International Strategy for Gender Equality (2018-2022) is a guiding instrument designed to coordinate France's efforts to improve the situation of women worldwide. The strategy is the international embodiment of the President's commitment to making gender equality a major national issue of his term. (16)

At the same time, the issue of gender equality has a strong influence on political life in France. President Emmanuel Macron's emphasis on gender equality raised much hope for feminist voters during the 2017 presidential campaign. As part of his pledge to support women's rights in France, Macron implemented protective policies for women. It established the Secretary for Equality between Women and Men position, currently held by Marlène Schiappa. Under Macron's leadership, France scored 75.1% in terms of the Gender Equality Index in 2020, ranking third best among all EU members. (17,18)

In this part, we saw how the rights and equality of men and women are ensured and violated in countries located on different continents of the world, whose language, religion, culture, and mentality differ from each other.

Steps taken to address inequality

We got acquainted with gender problems in different countries, and now let's see what steps should be taken to eliminate these problems. Because gender inequality is still maintained, the world community continues to take steps to eliminate it. Thus, in 2010, the Secretariat of the World Economic Forum in Geneva presented an integral indicator reflecting the inequality between men and women in terms of opportunities - the gender inequality index. Starting from 2010, this indicator was used in the United Nations Human Development Report every year, which clarified the existence of such a problem and led some countries to take measures to solve this problem.

Also, gender inequality is eliminated by creating several structures in the modern world. One such structure was established in 2010 within the United Nations Organization "Gender Equality and Women's Rights and Empowerment Issues." The executive board of this organization, better known as "UN-Women" (eng. UN Women), is represented by representatives of several countries. Among them: Somalia, Japan, Poland, Russia, New Zealand, Spain, Australia, etc. Great Britain, the United States of America, Mexico, Norway, Sweden, and Saudi Arabia deal with financing this structure and providing necessary resources.

One of the essential aspects of the mandate of "UN-Women" is the coordination and support of actions on the comprehensive accounting of the gender factor in the field of gender issues and within the entire UN system. On April 13, 2012, a systematic plan for gender equality and increasing the rights and opportunities of women was prepared and adopted at the meeting of the UN Coordination Council. Additionally, at the end of 2013, UN-Women established a constitutional database that reviews the constitutions of 195 UN member states about gender equality. The information in that database determines to what extent the legislative acts of these or other countries protect the rights and freedoms of women or in which countries they are oppressed.

Gender equality in Azerbaijan and the population's Attitude towards it

As we know, gender equality has been touched upon in different countries. We can include Azerbaijan in the list of those countries. During the last few decades, significant work has been done to promote gender equality in Azerbaijan. Equality of rights between all men and women is unequivocally established in the country's Constitution. The Republic of Azerbaijan has ratified several international agreements, including the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women, on promoting human rights and freedoms, and laws on the rise of gender equality and the fight against domestic violence have been adopted. In fact, we can see these activities from the APC period. An example is that the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, established in 1918, went down in history as the first republic in the East to give women the right to vote. As the first women's society in the Islamic world to receive the right to vote, Azerbaijani women have left behind their European and American counterparts in this respect. The unimaginable step for that period is also an indicator of the long and honorable history of the process of establishing a democratic and legal state in Azerbaijan. Thus, our country joined the Convention "On the Political Rights of Women" in 1992 and the Convention "On the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women" in 1995. The provision of equal rights and opportunities for men and women in the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, adopted in 1995, is one of the biggest steps taken in this direction. After that, in 1998, by the decree of the late President Heydar Aliyev, the State Committee on Women's Issues (now the State Committee on Family, Women, and Children's Issues) was established, the decrees "On measures to increase the role of women in Azerbaijan," in 2000 the "State Women The decree on the implementation of the policy" confirms that Heydar Aliyev is the guarantor of gender equality in Azerbaijan. According to the law "On Ensuring Gender Equality" adopted in our country in 2006, any discrimination based on gender is prohibited in Azerbaijan. The "Republican Comprehensive Program for Combating Everyday Violence in a Democratic Society," adopted by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated January 25, 2007, is one of the primary

documents that lay the foundation for combating gender-based violence in the country. (19)

The obtained results show that with the development of this type of legislation, compared to the beginning of the 20th century, women in the current period marry at an older age, give birth to fewer children, have almost the same opportunities to live in the countryside or in the city and come out of the household. They are more involved in activities that bring. However, current observations show that although women in our country have the same rights as men, the opportunities offered to men are not equally available to women. Although our women participate in all social spheres, politics, and business, positive changes are taking place. However, there is still a lot to be done, especially in the regions of the country.

Mehriban Zeynalova, the head of the "Tamiz Dünya" Public Union, believes that although there are specific problems in gender equality in Azerbaijan, there are also many positive things. Thus, women have been appointed to the positions of deputy heads of the executive, and other steps have been taken to increase the role of women in management: "However, it should be taken into account that gender equality is not measured only by personnel policy. Making several innovations in legislation is part of the gender equality policy. A balance has been created between women and men in municipal bodies. In the last municipal elections, a number of works were done in this direction. However, in contrast, is there a balance in the state institutions? It is difficult to say unequivocally. This balance has been disturbed in a number of areas. For example, there are more female teachers and doctors. In other words, there is still a need to do enough work in this field."

Sadiq Fataliyev, an expert on gender issues, underestimated the role of the media in communicating the current situation to the public: Thus, in recent years, mainly in the southern regions of Azerbaijan, women's rights have been violated. The media is content with informational information only. However, it is the responsibility of the press to investigate where these events originate, how they spread, and present them to the public. In this direction, you can find occasional articles. Mainly, the media writes articles about gender equality about the events held by some NGOs in Baku or regional centers. The same people usually attend such events. This causes the law not to reach the people without contact with the media, mainly the villagers. It can be said that they have no information about the events. To overcome all these and provide the public with broad knowledge about gender equality, it is necessary to start from the village. For this, every journalist should visit the villages and study the socio-economic situation of the population and the relationship between men and women. After that, he can introduce the public to the current situation by writing articles about gender equality."

S. Mammadli said that women in the regions are not very aware of gender equality. At the same time, there is a need to educate men in the regions to change their way of thinking. Most of the women and men in the regions think according to the mentality that a

woman's role is to take care of her husband and her family. But taking it to extremes hurts the situation. There is a difference between women's salaries. In the regions of Azerbaijan, women still do not have the same opportunities as men due to social problems, such as violence, exclusion from political and economic life, discrimination in employment, and difficulties in reconciling professional and personal life. (20)

According to MP Jala Aliyeva, who expressed her views on gender equality, Azerbaijani women represent modernity and independence as well as the East: "You know that in the East, men are more dominant, and women are brought up to be more submissive. In recent years, the topic of gender equality has been very It is true that it can be irritating in a certain sense. Still, I think it is important to reduce gender discrimination and restore the balance between the sexes. Imagine that there is still a difference in families between a girl child and a boy child. Sometimes even selective abortion is resorted to when they do not want it. I think it is necessary to implement more educational measures to prevent all this."

Lawyer Zulfiyya Bayramova approached the issue from a legal point of view. Women and men are equal before the law, but the only exception is that the law does not grant life imprisonment to women. Responsibility is similar in all other matters.

Shahla Ismayil, chairman of the Women's Society for Rational Development, believes that gender equality is not ensured in many areas. According to

him, gender equality in Azerbaijan is in a good state in terms of legislation, about 80 percent. He noted that despite some shortcomings in the laws, they generally create conditions for ensuring gender equality. Unfortunately, he emphasized that there are serious problems related to the implementation of this issue; therefore, gender equality is not guaranteed in many areas.

Referring to gender equality within the family, Shahla Ismayil said that no problem cannot be solved thanks to the right approach. He emphasized that both parties should be voluntary and take responsibility in establishing a family. Before starting a family, young people should be educated about family life and equal rights, and they should review gender stereotypes. Both parties must be able to negotiate, communicate with the other party, and listen to each other. There is no problem in the family that cannot be solved based on mutual respect. After marriage, economic freedom, especially the economic freedom of a woman, is very important. He said that this issue should be discussed even before starting a family. Studies show that a working woman creates a more comfortable environment in the family than a housewife, where understanding is more favorable. (21)

Our survey in Azerbaijan reflects the realities of gender equality in this society. Five hundred eighty-five people participated in the survey. The results are given below:

In your opinion, to what extent is equality between men and women ensured in Azerbaijan?

■ Provided. ■ Partially secured. ■ Not guaranteed at all. ■ It is provided but there are shortcomings.

Which gender do you think gender inequality affects the most?

■ Women ■ Men ■ To both ■

Sales

■ Boy ■ Girl ■ It does not matter ■

CONCLUSION

Based on the information we obtained from various sources and the survey we conducted, it is evident that gender equality is an urgent problem in the world. In general, to solve the problem from the root, education should be done first. It is necessary to promote this

process to citizens both in educational institutions and through various events. One of the main steps is to advertise on social media, a suitable means of communication today to promote gender equality. Legal punishment of those who violate gender equality can be mentioned as one of the ways out.

References

1. Bayramova Y. (2022), Gender bərabərliyi Azərbaycanca necə tənzimlənir?
2. Cabbarlı N. (2021), Gender bərabərliyi nə deməkdir?
3. Martinez H. (2022), What is gender equality? Learn the definition with examples.
4. Italy | European Institute for Gender Equality (Europa. eu)
5. Country Fact Sheet | UN Women Data Hub
6. Gangemi A.- Costantino T. Gender gap in Italy: equality is still a mirage
7. GENDER EQUALITY IN TURKEY (2012)
8. Turkey Global gender gap index, 2006-2022 - knoema.com
9. Türkiye | UN Women – Europe and Central Asia
10. Telseren A. (2022), Gender in/Equality and Feminism in Turkey
11. UNICEF, Gender equality in India
12. Women's rights in Iran - Wikipedia
13. WATCH: Women and girls are still protesting in Iran. Here's why | PBS NewsHour
14. Iran: Women and girls treated as second class citizens, reforms urgently needed, says UN expert | OHCHR
15. Esfandiari H. (2022), Violence Against Women: A Never-Ending Story in Iran
16. France's international strategy for gender equality (2018-2022), 2021.
17. Stolar S. (2021), WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN FRANCE: ACTIVISM AND EFFORTS
18. Gender equality: a priority for France, (2021)
19. Gender (kişi və qadınların) bərabərliyinin təminatları haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikasının qanunu, Bakı şəhəri, 10 oktyabr 2006-cı il № 150-IIIQ
20. Cavid Şahverdiyev, Xalq Cəbhəsi. - 2015 .- 17 iyun.-S.11.
21. Cavid ŞÜKÜROV,525-ci qəzet. - 2016.- 3 mart.- S.8.